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Report on First EOSC EDEN/FIDELIS Bootcamp

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Executive Summary

A key activity of the EOSC EDEN project is the delivery of a series of bootcamps to showcase and engage the relevant stakeholders in the repository and digital preservation communities towards co-creation and adoption of the project's results. The bootcamps are an activity that seeks alignment with the engagement and training activities of the FIDELIS project, a sister project to EOSC EDEN aiming to create a European network of trustworthy digital repositories. The 1st EOSC EDEN/FIDELIS Bootcamp took place in November 2025 as a face-to-face event in Paris, France, and provided an early opportunity for the community to engage with the two projects, learn about the outputs being generated and networks that they are building for their benefit, and contribute to discussions that are useful for further development of the projects' activities.

1 Introduction

The EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects started in January 2025 and were set up to be complementary in their objectives, where the FIDELIS project aims to establish a European network of trustworthy digital repositories (TDRs), and represents a major part of the communities targeted by EOSC EDEN.

EOSC EDEN:

“The EOSC EDEN project (grant agreement nr.101188015) seeks to enhance digital preservation strategies at European and National level. At its core, the project will create **a comprehensive framework** to identify what data are candidates for digital preservation. This involves **setting standards and protocols** for long-term data preservation, which will be determined through **an assessment** of data usage, quality, and the data’s benefits to science and society.

In addition to the framework, the EOSC EDEN project aims to **develop a model for re-appraisal of data** throughout its lifecycle. The model’s usability and practicality will be assessed through relevant communities (the early adopters), which will also help in **developing tools and services** to automate certain preservation actions. The model for re-appraisal will support the framework for digital preservation by ensuring that preservation efforts remain relevant over time.”¹

EOSC FIDELIS:

“The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) aims to develop a web of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data and services for science in Europe. **The FIDELIS project (grant agreement no. 101188078)** will enhance **the sustainability of EOSC**, by establishing a network of healthy, vibrant and self-sustaining trustworthy digital repositories (TDRs).

Within its three-year lifetime, FIDELIS project **establishes and operates** a European network of TDRs, fostering their **harmonisation and interoperability** across repositories. It will provide a framework to support repositories in becoming and remaining trustworthy and FAIR-enabling over time. FIDELIS also contributes to the upskilling of repositories and expansion of TDR Network, by offering a series of training and financial support programme.”²

The EOSC EDEN project is tasked with the organisation of *at least* three bootcamps, aiming to foster co-creation, engagement, alignment and uptake of project outputs both within the two projects but also towards external communities.

¹ <https://eden-fidelis.eu/about-us>

² *Ibid*

2 Organisation and Preparation

The organisation of the Bootcamp was led by the EOSC EDEN project and, more specifically, the task responsible for engagement and synchronisation with relevant EOSC projects and initiatives. Four sessions were planned at the first bootcamp, with three dedicated to EOSC EDEN work that focussed on (i) data and process framework for long-term digital preservation, (ii) long-term access and preservation services and tools, and (iii) discipline-specific requirements, validation and future use. The other session was dedicated to presenting work from FIDELIS and establishing a TDR Network which involves three consecutive year-long phases: (i) preparing and establishing the network, (ii) consolidating the TDR Network and adding value, and (iii) transitioning the TDR Network and adding value to sustainability. In so doing, the Bootcamp provided an early opportunity in the lifetimes of the two projects to disseminate the principles on which they were founded and solicit participation, especially through the network aspects (see below).

2.1 Delivery

On 19th November, 2025 the first of these bootcamps took place in Paris in a commercial venue, one day after the inaugural RDA Europe Summit³, and was organised in a manner that would attract key stakeholders attending that conference of both the EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects. The Bootcamp was open to all stakeholders, with a particular focus on those involved in the digital research repository community, and including some project partners. The opportunity for these experts and interested parties to meet in person and discuss the shared objectives of the EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects and those of the audience was met enthusiastically as the issue of long-term data preservation is acknowledged to be a pressing concern. Indeed, one aspect - although not explicitly stated during the event - is the impact from today's geopolitical climate and the safeguarding of research data, and data sovereignty.

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/events/rda-europe-annual-summit/>

Table 1- Agenda of the 1st EOSC EDEN/FIDELIS Bootcamp, 19th Nov, 2025, Paris. Also shown below are two pictures taken on the day of the setup at the venue.

Time	Topic	Speaker	Additional Info
08:30-08:45 CET	Welcome and information on the sessions	S. Venkataraman, DANS	Housekeeping and brief overview of the EDEN and FIDELIS projects.
08:45-09:30 CET	EOSC EDEN User Journey Maps and Pilot Methodology	Giacomo Cannizzaro, SURF	<i>Presentation on the work of User Journey Maps and Pilot Methodology.</i> <i>Discussion on topic and feedback from the repository community and general audience.</i>
09:30 - 10:15 CET	EOSC EDEN specifications and architecture for long-term access and preservation services	Wim Hugo, DANS	<i>Presentation of the first iteration of the EOSC EDEN specifications and architecture for long-term access and preservation services.</i> <i>Discussion on topic and feedback from the repository community and general audience</i>
10:15-10:45 CET	Coffee Break and networking		
10:45-11:30 CET	EOSC EDEN Core Preservation Processes	Bertrand Caron, TIB	<i>Introduction to Core Preservation Processes: What are they? Why are they important?</i> <i>Walk-through of structured CPP description. Show-casing CPP relationships. Exercise / Discussion using 1 CPP example.</i>
11:30-12:15 CET	Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories	S. Venkataraman, DANS	<i>Introduction and overview of the work of the FIDELIS project towards a Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories.</i> <i>Discussion, engagement and feedback from the repository community and general audience</i>
12:15-12:30 CET	Open discussion, conclusions, next steps and closing		

EOSC EDEN presented work on “discipline-specific requirements, validation and future use”⁴ and which essentially involves the identification of end-user (typically researchers) requirements, and validation of outputs from the EDEN project that will make end-users’ lives easier in the safeguarding of their digital research outputs. The latter is being done through project partners themselves that cover a spectrum of research disciplines including social sciences and humanities, life sciences and physical sciences.

The second session was more technical relating to “specifications and architecture for long-term access and preservation services”⁵, and provided a comprehensive overview of activities and also in relation to work that is soon going to be completed in the RDA Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG)⁶.

Meanwhile, session three presented the work on “core preservation processes (CPPs)”⁷ and which is looking at research data (re)appraisal and what attributes a research data object presents that makes it a candidate for long-term preservation. This session was then able to engage the audience in their experiences and expertise on how file formats and other aspects of good data management practices will need to be considered and especially in relation to generating a set of CPPs.

Rounding out the Bootcamp was a session dedicated to discussion of the FIDELIS TDR Network. This is one of the key objectives of the EOSC FIDELIS project whereby a network of European repositories are being invited to gather to address common challenges and provide support to each other through knowledge exchange and community building. These are all within the context of building the EOSC and promoting TRUST⁸ and FAIR⁹ principles. At the time of writing, and also when the Bootcamp was delivered, the TDR Network was well on its way to meeting initial targets on the number of repositories that joined the Network (>60¹⁰) and the Bootcamp provided an opportune moment to take stock of where it is, and crucially its future direction(s). Participants were divided into two groups to discuss the latter and provide suggestions on what they thought and were especially asked to think about the context with the EOSC EDEN objectives and outputs that were presented in the other three sessions of the Bootcamp. This feedback could then be used in future alignment activities of the two projects since there will be many opportunities for cross-pollination.

2.2 Suggested future directions to align EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects

Presented below is a distillation of some of the suggestions that were made by the participants of the Bootcamp in the final session described above.

⁴ Andreassen *et al.* (2025) D3.1 - Report on Discipline Requirements and Needs. *Zenodo*. <https://zenodo.org/records/15789261>

⁵ Middelbos *et al.* (2025) D2.1 - EOSC EDEN Specifications and Architecture (Iteration 1). *Zenodo*. <https://zenodo.org/records/17232536>

⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/community-based-catalogue-requirements-trustworthy-technical-repository-service-providers/activit/y/>

⁷ EOSC EDEN T1.2 *et al.* (2025) M1.1 Report on Identification of Core Preservation Processes. *Zenodo*. <https://zenodo.org/records/16992452>

⁸ Lin *et al.* (2020) The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Sci Data* 7, 144. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>

⁹ Wilkinson *et al.* (2016) The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

¹⁰ Venkataraman *et al.* (2025) D2.2 - FIDELIS TDR Network Establishment. *Zenodo*. <https://zenodo.org/records/17976725>

2.2.1. FIDELIS TDR Network, EDEN Curation Network and EDEN Outputs

Embedding of the EOSC EDEN Expert Curation and Digital Preservation Network into the FIDELIS TDR Network was one of the first suggestions. Indeed, this is already being explored by the two project teams involved in setting up the two networks. The EOSC EDEN Expert Curation and Digital Preservation Network is a separate entity but which could have significant synergies with the FIDELIS TDR Network, and therefore if there are many individuals within the TDR Network member repositories that have curation expertise, or wish to learn more, this would be a logical step.

At the time of writing, the TDR Network is already investigating ways to establish itself as a self-sufficient entity which will live on beyond the lifetime of the projects, and the manner in which it will be sustainable and how it will be governed. These factors could have a direct bearing on the Expert Curation and Digital Preservation Network, if they become connected in some way, and the EOSC EDEN project in general with the outputs that it is generating including the CPPs.

Indeed, it was further suggested that the TDR Network could maintain a Github repository with the CPPs and that working group(s) could be a structured way to focus on a topic and assign responsibilities to maintain outputs. The discussion also recognised that there can be multiple choices as to who is in charge of maintaining certain outputs, and that if there are already well-established organisations and/or networks, that these could continue the maintenance. Depending on the type of output, the appropriate venue must be identified, with choices such as the Research Data Alliance (RDA)¹¹ or Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC)¹². For example, one possible avenue to explore in this case would be for the FIDELIS TDR Network to establish and help run RDA interest or working groups, a common practice in the RDA community and which places the responsibility on a well-established global community of experts.

Other observations and suggestions made by the participants included that policies are often conservative due to the required resources. In this case, EOSC EDEN could help automate some tasks, such as flagging file formats at risk to the community, which would significantly reduce resources required.

2.2.3 Training and Outreach

Discussions and suggestions from participants during the Bootcamp also extended towards the training and outreach aspects of the projects. The FIDELIS project's objectives aim more towards network building and exchanging best practices, especially through its TDR Network. Together with activities in EOSC EDEN such as the building of its Expert Curation and Digital Preservation Network, training for curation/preservation specialists and experts is a consideration to be explored and to bring this at the European level, while facilitating networking with peers, such as exchanging experience of preservation policies and the practical implementation challenges.

It was noted that there are already some national trainings/courses being established to train and certify support specialists, and that these could be approached to possibly align such activities with those in EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS. It was also asserted that digital preservation training and

¹¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

¹² <https://www.dpconline.org/>

digital archival courses are mostly institutional at present and that there is a weak link to research data management (RDM) at a wider level. For example, in Germany, NESTOR¹³ is national, and bridging training between this and institutional communities could be a suggestion to be taken into account in the context of the FIDELIS support and training activities. Expert Curation and Digital Preservation Network activities for repositories. Moreover, another key challenge identified by the participants was to empower IT staff to understand why and how curation experts implement their best practices. Therefore, when considering the above, EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS project, TDR Network and Expert Curation and Digital Preservation Network activities should broaden the audience to IT professionals of service providers, including repositories and archives, to stimulate knowledge exchange and bridge the gap. This also extends to bridging the gap between EOSC EDEN work on long-term access and preservation services and tools and the Expert Curation and Digital Preservation Network specialists who need to understand and work together.

3 Next Bootcamp

The next bootcamp is already being planned, due to take place on 16th February 2026 in Zagreb, Croatia - this time being co-located with the IDCC26¹⁴ conference. The 2nd Bootcamp will present more from the key outcomes and outputs of EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS, such as the Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix (TTRAM; a key output of FIDELIS which was not given a session devoted to it in the 1st Bootcamp)¹⁵, the outputs described above, consolidate recent results, and offer opportunities for participation in interactive sessions. The co-location of the Bootcamp with one of the major annual conferences in the international digital curation community will also provide an opportunity to bring together a wide range of stakeholders, whether in terms of expertise or geography.

4 Conclusions and next steps

The 1st EOSC EDEN/FIDELIS Bootcamp aimed to bring together repository and curation community experts to empower them with the knowledge and tools that are being developed, by fostering engagement and uptake through co-creation and interaction. Moreover, the Bootcamps provide a forum for community building and which is essential to the two projects' journey in implementing their activities in a way that serves and empowers the key target communities.

In this first year of the projects, this Bootcamp allowed early results and information to be shared, and provided a foundation for the further development of EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS outputs, which can be iteratively showcased and discussed at future Bootcamps. Project partners directly involved in the engagement, outreach and training are actively seeking to make the outputs of the projects more relatable and understandable to the repository and digital preservation communities since this will impact the success of the projects.

¹³ https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de/Webs/nestor/EN/nestor/nestor_node.html

¹⁴ <https://dcc.ac.uk/events/idcc>

¹⁵ Kleemola *et al.* (2025) FIDELIS MS12 First version of TTRAM. *Zenodo*. <https://zenodo.org/records/17157958>